

An Approach to Quantify the Negative Capacitance Features in a Triple-Cation based Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

Understanding the device kinetics occurring in the bulk and charge selective layers is vital for optimizing the performance of perovskite solar cells (PSCs) and their development. We studied planar PSCs with and without hole transport layer (HTL) and measured hysteresis free power conversion efficiency of 16.23% with poly(3-hexylthiophene) [P3HT] as HTL, while the PSCs without HTL showed significant hysteresis. We investigated a comprehensive electrical response of the PSCs. The bias-dependent electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) revealed the appearance of the negative capacitance in the low-frequency regime. The modification of the low-frequency PSCs response accompanied by a further decrease in recombination resistance is due to the interfacial interactions between the migrating ions and the metal contact. The doped and undoped P3HT layers impeded this interaction which explains the absence of the negative capacitance at lower applied voltages. Our investigation provides an understanding of the physical processes behind the negative capacitance.

KEYWORDS: perovskite, P3HT, hole transport materials, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, negative capacitance.

Introduction

Halide-based perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have experienced a boosted development and power conversion efficiency (PCE) surge from 3.8% in 2009 to the current 25.5% [1-4]. Perovskite materials have a general formula of ABX_3 , where A, B, and X represent organic cations (methylammonium ($CH_3NH_3^+$, MA^+), formamidinium ($CH_3(NH_2)^{2+}$, FA^+) and Cesium (Cs^+), etc.); divalent metal cations (Pb^{2+} or Sn^{2+}) and halide anions (I, Br and Cl), respectively [5]. The significant enhancement in PCEs can be attributed to the exceptional properties of perovskites, such as strong light absorption, tunable direct bandgap, high charge carrier mobility, long carrier lifetime and diffusion length, and solution processability [6-9]. Despite the rapid improvement in PCE, PSCs display issues such as current-voltage ($J-V$) hysteresis and instability under prolonged operational conditions [10,11]. The mismatch of the current measured during the sweeping in the two bias directions remains an open challenge to address the reliability of PSCs [12]. Recently, several groups have studied possible causes for the hysteretic behavior: (i) charge trapping/detrapping, (ii) ferroelectric polarization, (iii) migration of the excess ions due to interstitial defects, (iv) charge accumulation at the interfaces, and (v) unbalanced charge carrier transport [13-16]. The selective contact/perovskite interfaces play a pivotal role in controlling the mechanisms of the charge extraction capability, accumulation, and recombination. Therefore, knowledge and understanding of the physical processes taking place in the bulk and interfacial layers are of utmost interest to intensely comprehend PSCs peculiarities for the pursuit of performance enhancement [17]. Toward this end, several methods have been used to probe correlated charge carrier kinetics in PSCs including low-frequency noise (LFN) [18], open-circuit voltage decay measurements [19], photocurrent spectroscopy [20], and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) [21]. EIS provides information regarding the electrical response (resistive and capacitive processes) on different timescales with high sensitivity. However, the analysis of EIS results requires the use of a suitable equivalent circuit. They can vary depending

on the applied voltage and become arbitrarily complex, especially when inductive elements are present which are puzzling. Beyond the inductive loop behavior at intermediate frequencies in the EIS plots, a negative capacitance at low frequencies was observed in the PSCs, a challenging behavior to decode [22-24]. This has been addressed in recent studies, but its physical origin is not yet conclusively identified. Negative capacitance has a deleterious effect on performance, through its contribution to the reduction of open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), fill factor (FF), and subsequently leading to the reduction in the PCE [25]. Negative capacitance is not only a peculiar effect observed in low performing solar cells but is also noted in the efficient PSCs [26]. One hypothesis to interpret the negative capacitance is that the interaction of ionic and electronic effects produces delayed dynamics, either by charge accumulation at the interface or by ionic redistribution controlling charge injection [27,28]. On the other hand, it is a possible intrinsic instability of the device during the measurement of EIS, and the phenomenon is recently observed in perovskite-based ReRAM devices [29]. An explanation for the negative capacitance effect and phase-delayed recombination through mobile ions [30] was proposed theoretically, and the low-frequency capacitance (positive and negative) is a natural consequence of slow transients in injection current, which was correlated with hysteresis in J - V curves measured in the dark was noted [31]. However, the phenomenological origin of the negative capacitance is not conclusively identified yet. In a typical planar n - i - p based PSC structure, the perovskite absorber layer is sandwiched between electron and hole transport layers (ETL and HTL), respectively. Arguably, the HTL in PSCs is responsible for extracting hole carriers, and it plays a pivotal role in interfacial properties and charge transport kinetics. Poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT) is one of the well-known and extensively studied polymers as an HTL, owing to its unique properties, such as high charge mobility ($0.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), wide bandgap, good solubility, thermal stability, and low cost (10 times cheaper than Spiro-OMeTAD) [32-36]. In this work, we used doped and undoped P3HT as an HTL for the fabrication of planar (n - i - p) PSCs with a structure

of FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/Cs_{0.1}(FAPbI₃)_{0.81}(MAPbBr₃)_{0.09}/HTL/Au. We investigated the influence of HTL on the photovoltaic performance, hysteresis, and EIS response of the PSCs. We noted the presence of the low-frequency negative capacitance feature in EIS plots, which is higher for the HTL-free PSCs as compared to the PSCs with HTL. Furthermore, we elucidated the influence of HTL on device performance through the temperature-dependent admittance spectroscopy and Mott-Schottky analysis.

Experimental Part

Device fabrication

In this study, we fabricated three types of planar PSCs designated as D1, D2, and D3 henceforth of the following architectures:

1. D1- FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/CsFAMA/Au.
2. D2- FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/CsFAMA/P3HT/Au.
3. D3- FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/CsFAMA/P3HT:Li+t-BP/Au.

Firstly, the FTO-coated substrates were cleaned through ultrasonicated for 20 min in Hellmanex II solution, followed by de-ionized water, acetone, and isopropanol, and finally dried using compressed air. The substrates were further treated by UV-ozone for 30 min. TiO₂ compact (c-TiO₂) layer was deposited onto the patterned FTO by spray pyrolysis at 500°C using titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) precursor solution (1:19 v/v ratio in pure ethanol) using oxygen as a carrier gas. The substrates were then kept for 30 min at 500°C for the formation of the anatase phase. When the substrates attained room temperature, an electron transport layer of SnO₂-QD was deposited by spin coating atop of TiO₂ compact layer, followed by a progressive heating step until 200°C for 1h. Subsequently, we immediately transferred the samples inside the Argon-filled glovebox under controlled moisture and oxygen conditions (H₂O level: <1 ppm and

O₂ level: <10 ppm) for the deposition of perovskite and HTL. The triple cation perovskite precursor solution containing CsI (0.10 M), FAI (1.05 M), PbI₂ (1.24 M), MABr (0.12 M), and PbBr₂ (0.12 M) was prepared in a mixed solvent of DMF and DMSO (volume ratio 4:1). The perovskite solution was spin-coated in a two-step program at 1000 and 6000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second step, 112 μL of chlorobenzene was poured on the spinning substrates after 20 s, and the substrate was annealed at 100 °C for 60 min. Subsequently, the HTL, undoped-P3HT (10 mg of P3HT/ml of chlorobenzene) and doped P3HT with Li-TFSI (7 μL of *t*-BP and 10 μL of Lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (170 mg/mL in acetonitrile)), the solution was deposited by spin coating at 5000 for 30 s on top of the perovskite layer. The device was finished by depositing 80 nm of gold by a thermal evaporator under a vacuum level between 10⁻⁶ – 10⁻⁵ torr.

Thin Film Characterization: The absorption spectra were acquired by a UV-vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer). X-ray diffractograms were recorded using a D8 Advance diffractometer from Bruker (Bragg-Brentano geometry, with an X-ray tube Cu K α , $\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). A scan range of 3–80° was selected with an acquisition time of 1° per min. A Field emission scanning electron microscope (Hitachi S-4800) was used to capture the cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the samples. The hydrophobicity of the films was assessed by measuring the contact angle of a water droplet on the film surface by using a contact angle goniometer (Ossila).

Device Characterization: The photovoltaic characteristics of PSCs were measured under irradiation of 1000 W/m² (AM1.5, 1 sun) provided by an Oriel solar simulator (Newport). The active area of the devices was 0.09 cm² that was controlled by using a black metal mask. The incident photon-to-current efficiency (IPCE) spectra were recorded by using a 150W Xenon lamp attached to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4m monochromator. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out using BioLogic SP-300 Potentiostat in the

frequency range of 2 MHz - 1 mHz under the 20 mV perturbation. The capacitance-frequency measurements at different temperatures were performed with a Keysight precision LCR meter (model E4980A) along with a Linkam (LTS420) heating control system.

Results and Discussions

The UV-vis absorbance spectra of the doped and undoped P3HT layers deposited on the CsFAMA layer and the glass substrates are shown (Figure 1a), the triple cation perovskite absorbs across the whole visible region with an edge at 785 nm. CsFAMA absorption is slightly extended when covered by the P3HT layer (Figure 1a). This is originated from the absorption of pristine P3HT. It can be deduced (inset of Figure 1a), the P3HT layer displays a broad absorption peak in the 400-650 nm wavelength range. The absorbance peak at 528 nm suggests the degree of conjugation in the P3HT chains, while the shoulders at 553 and 604 nm are related to the interchain order [37,38]. While, with the doping of P3HT, a slight redshift and enhancement of the absorbance spectra can be observed, this extended light absorption will make a slight contribution to the photocurrent.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns (Figure 1b) show identical diffraction patterns. The XRD patterns of the samples do not show any additional diffraction peaks for both pristine and doped P3HT when deposited on perovskite, suggesting the amorphous nature of the polymer. The peaks at 14.22° , 20.07° , 24.70° , 28.49° , 31.95° , 34.98° , 40.65° , and 43.20° , corresponding to the (101), (012), (021), (202), (211), (122), (024), and (131) are in agreement with the formation of the tetragonal phase in 3-dimensional perovskite. On the other hand, the intensity of the main diffraction peaks slightly increases, indicating improved crystallization.

Figure 1: (a) UV-Vis absorbance spectra, and (b) XRD patterns of CsFAMA, CsFAMA/pristine-P3HT and CsFAMA/doped-P3HT layers.

Planar PSCs with the *n-i-p* structure of FTO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂-QD/CsFAMA/HTL/Au were fabricated by using pristine-P3HT, P3HT doped with Li+t-BP as HTL, and without HTL (Figure 2a). Expectedly, the cross-sectional micrograph display structure with well-defined interfaces and the thickness of the different layers can be visualized (Figure S1). The energy level alignment of the materials used for the PSC (Figure 2b) fabrication, where SnO₂ quantum dots is used as electron selective layer together with c-TiO₂ to enhance hole-blocking ability. The typical *J-V* curves of the PSC are disclosed (Figure 2c), and the photovoltaic parameters are tabulated (Table 1). The PCE of types D1, D2, and D3 are 6.37%, 15.19%, and 16.23% respectively, suggesting the decisive role of HTL on PSC performance. The obtained PCE values are among the highest reported PCE for triple cation-based PSCs using P3HT as HTL without any interlayer at the perovskite/P3HT interface. The pristine-P3HT-based PSC displayed a PCE of 15.19% which is significantly higher than the value of the pristine Spiro-OMeTAD (5.14%) [39]. Remarkably, the PSCs with HTL were almost hysteresis-free (Table

1 and Figure S2). In contrast, the HTL free PSC shows a high value of hysteresis index, signaling the absence of HTL can induce ionic accumulation at the perovskite/charge selective layer interface. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra of the PSCs were recorded to probe the integrated photocurrent density (Figure 2d). It is evident that the PSCs with HTL exhibit higher EQE, around 85%, in the broad wavelength range from 400-800 nm than the HTL free PSCs. The integrated J_{sc} values calculated from EQE are 14.64, 22.37, and 22.66 mA/cm² for D1, D2, and D3, respectively, which are marginally lower than the J_{sc} values measured from the J - V curves. This difference is attributed to the presence of shallow trap states at the interfaces of the perovskite/charge selective layer interface [40]. The loss of electron generated by the weaker monochromatic light used in the EQE measurement at the perovskite/charge selective contact interface becomes severe as a consequence of the trapping process, while these trap states can be filled up under high illumination intensity as in the case of the J - V measurement, leading to the mismatch between two measurements [41].

Figure 2: (a) Device architecture, (b) energy level diagram of the PSC, (c) J - V curves for the PSCs devices with and without HTL, and (d) EQE spectra and integrated current density of the corresponding PSCs.

Table 1: Photovoltaic parameters of the PSCs with and without HTL.

Device	Scan direction	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mAcm^{-2})	FF (%)	PCE (%)	HI
HTL free (D1)	RS	868.65	16.49	44.43	6.37	0.43
	FS	649.98	18.16	30.32	3.58	
Pristine P3HT (D2)	RS	973.31	24.24	64.37	15.19	0.039
	FS	976.29	24.57	60.85	14.59	
Doped P3HT (D3)	RS	897.48	24.84	72.79	16.23	0.062
	FS	903.67	24.16	67.43	15.22	

HI: hysteresis index defined as $\left[\frac{J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})} - J_{FS(0.8 v_{oc})}}{J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})}} \right]$ where $J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})}$ and $J_{FS(0.8 v_{oc})}$ represent the J_{sc} at 80% of v_{oc} of the reverse and forward scan, respectively.

To gain a deeper insight into the effect of the HTL on the charge (ions, electrons, and holes) transport and accumulation at the interfaces, we probed the fabricated PSCs by EIS [42.43].

Figure 3 shows the complex impedance plots of PSCs recorded in the 1 MHz – 10 mHz range at different dc voltages (V_{app}) varying from the short circuit to the open circuit conditions. All the recorded spectra exhibit different behavior at low frequencies (LF) depending on applied dc voltage. At low applied voltages, two main circle arcs are observed at high frequency (HF) and lower frequency (LF) ranges. However, when the applied voltage increases, the low-frequency arc collapses into an arc below the x-axis (the real impedance axis Z'). This arc is attributed to the presence of negative capacitance. It can be deduced (Figure 3) that the negative capacitance feature for HTL-free PSCs (D1) appeared clearly at a low applied voltage (starting from 0.3V), while for PSCs with HTL (D2 and D3) they appeared at higher applied voltages. In addition, the negative capacitance feature is more pronounced in the case of HTL-free PSCs. Expectedly, the presence of the hole transport layer plays an important role to minimize this feature. Moreover, the capacitance-frequency plots (Figure S3) show that the negative capacitance occurred in the low-frequency region (<100 Hz) for the three types of PSCs. The impedance data can be fitted using equivalent electrical circuits (EECs) shown in **Figure S4**, where R_1 represents the series resistance contributions of FTO, gold, and electrical wires; C_2 and R_2 are responsible for the high-frequency arc related to geometric capacitance of the perovskite and bulk recombination resistance; C_3 describes the charge accumulation capacitance at the perovskite/charge selective interface, and that is together with R_3 (related to interfacial charge transfer resistance) accounts for the low-frequency arc [44-46]. The inductor element (L) is used in parallel with R_3 and C_3 to fit the region of negative capacitance observed

at low frequencies. The extracted parameters from the EIS fitting for the PSCs, using the EC-Lab software, are presented (Table S1a-c). No significant change in C_2 was observed with the applied voltages, confirming that C_2 is mainly related to the intrinsic dielectric relaxation of the bulk perovskite [47,48]. This capacitance has been expressed by $C_2 = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r A}{d}$, with ϵ_r the relative permittivity, ϵ_0 the vacuum permittivity (8.85×10^{-12} F/m), A the cell surface area, and d the perovskite layer thickness. Taking $A = 0.49$ cm², $\epsilon_r = 41$ [49], and $d = 390$ nm, we obtain $C_2 = 45 \times 10^{-9}$ F, which is in agreement with the same order of magnitude for the experimental data (Table S1). On the other hand, the accumulation capacitance at the LF region can be up to 1000 orders of magnitude larger than the high-frequency geometric capacitance (C_2) of the perovskite layer. This is because the accumulated ions near interfaces only respond to AC signals at low frequencies, and thus originating the apparent excess capacitance at LF [50].

R_2 , R_3 are the recombination resistances, in which R_3 originates from the recombinations occurring at or near the interfaces. In particular, a mixed ionic-electronic nature of CsFAMA perovskite induces the movement of ions due to perturbation of the voltage, introducing defects that can be behaved as recombination centers, and consequently the hindered charge transfer dynamics. The recombination resistance varies inversely with the recombination rate, it is found that both resistances of R_2 and R_3 of the D2 and D3 devices are higher than that of the D1 device (Table 2). The higher values of recombination resistance signify the reduced recombination rate and less trap-related recombination in HTL based devices [51]. Additionally, this parameter for the doped-P3HT is higher than that of the undoped-P3HT based PSC, suggesting a reduction

of recombination losses due to the $\text{Li}^+t\text{-BP}$ effect [52]. These results are consistent with the PSC performance obtained from the J - V measurements. The low-frequency resistance gradually decreases with an increase in applied voltage, signifying altered interface at perovskite/charge selective layer due to the migration of ions. Further reduction in resistance manifested by the low-frequency negative arcs indicates an interaction of ions with the cathode (Au metal) contact. This indicates that the P3HT acts as an efficient barrier layer inhibiting the interaction between migrating ions and the Au contact at lower applied voltages. It was reported that the reactivity of migrating ions with interfacial defects causes a reduction in recombination resistance [53]. To further quantify the HTL impact on the PSC performance, we performed the temperature-dependent admittance spectroscopy in combination with Mott-Schottky analysis.

Figure 3: Nyquist plots at different applied dc voltages under dark conditions for the PSC, (a) without HTL (D1), (b) with pristine P3HT (D2), and (c) with doped P3HT (D3).

Figure 4 displays the capacitance as a function of frequency measured at different temperatures. These $C-f$ plots can be divided into three distinct regions in which the low frequencies (20 Hz-500 Hz) capacitance corresponds to the electronic and ionic accumulation and involves the defect state at the interfaces of perovskite and charge selective layers [54,55]. The capacitive response produced at the intermediate-frequency (IF) region (500 Hz-20 kHz) is associated with the intrinsic dielectric polarization of the perovskite layer which is determined by the geometrical capacitance. The temperature-independent constant value of capacitance at the IF

region suggests the stable geometrical capacitance associated with the perovskite layer. While in the range of high frequencies (20 kHz-2 MHz), capacitance rapidly decreases with frequency and does not change with temperature. This sharp decrease in capacitance is due to the effect of the series resistance of contact electrodes. Particularly, at the LF region, a significantly enhanced thermally-activated capacitance could be observed. Figure 5a shows the temperature dependence low frequency (≈ 52 Hz) capacitance of CsFAMA based PSCs. It can be noted that the capacitance increases exponentially with the temperature. This increase of the capacitance is caused by the coupled effect of ionic as well as electronic processes taking place at the interfaces [56]. This high value of capacitance with an increase of temperature in the LF region can be majorly contributed to the movement of ions that are located in the deep energy location within the bandgap [57,58]. We noted that the capacitance value for the D1 is always higher than that of D2 and D3 throughout the temperatures range, which can be ascribed to the higher ion concentration accumulation induced phenomena at the interface of perovskite/Au compared to perovskite/HTL. The unbalance charge extraction at the interfaces in PSCs without HTL allows the capacitance to build up, causing hysteresis in $J-V$ plots [59].

Figure 4: Capacitance vs variable frequency at different temperatures for the PSC, (a) without HTL, (b) with pristine P3HT, and (c) with doped P3HT.

The temperature-dependent conductance responses from PSCs (**Figure S5**) are also consistent with their corresponding capacitance. The conductance increases with the increase in frequency up to a certain value and attains a peak at higher frequencies. This is due to the dielectric freeze-out phenomenon [60,61]. By plotting the conductance measured at ≈ 52 Hz as a function of the temperature (Figure 5b), one can observe an exponential increase of conductance with

temperature. The PSCs with HTL gave the highest conductance as compared to HTL free PSC, pointing toward higher charge transfer at perovskite/P3HT interfaces.

Figure 5: (a) Temperature dependence low-frequency capacitance and, (b) temperature dependence low-frequency conductance of the PSCs.

The depletion width (W) can be measured by analyzing the built-in potential (V_{bi}) at the perovskite/HTL interface, which is estimated from the intersection of the linear part of the Mott-Schottky plot on the bias axis (Figure 6). The Mott-Schottky characteristic is expressed by the following formula [62,63]:

$$\frac{1}{C^2} = \frac{2}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r q N A^2} (V_{bi} - V)$$

Where ϵ_0 , ϵ_r , V , A and q is the vacuum permittivity, relative permittivity, applied bias voltage, active area surface, and elementary charge, respectively. N represents the doping density of immobile ions at depletion region in perovskite side and was determined from the slope of the linear region. We can deduce (Table 2), that the built-in potential for the fabricated PSCs increased from 870 mV for HTL free to >1000 mV for HTL based PSCs (Table 2). In principle, a larger V_{bi} not only offers a greater driving force for the separation of photo-induced charge carriers but also effectively prevents the carriers from going back from HTL to the perovskite layer [64]. The HTL-free PSC shows an immobile dopants density of $1.88 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which

increases to $2.11 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $2.14 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the undoped and doped P3HT based PSCs, respectively.

With the doping density known, the depletion width of the active layer (W) can be calculated

$$\text{by: } W = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_0\epsilon_r V_{bi}}{qN}}$$

The depletion width increased from 144.87 nm for HTL free PSCs to 148.07 nm for the undoped-P3HT and 148.46 nm for the doped-P3HT based PSCs. The improved depletion region assists in the proper charge dissociation and annihilates the recombination, and thus contributes to the enhancement of photovoltaic performance.

Figure 6: Mott-Schottky (C^{-2} - V) plots of the devices at 10 kHz.

Table 2: Electrical parameters extracted from Mott-Schottky analysis.

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>D1 (without HTL)</i>	<i>D2 (with Pristine P3HT)</i>	<i>D3 (with Doped P3HT)</i>
V_{bi} (V)	0.87	1.02	1.04
N (10^{17} cm^{-3})	1.88	2.11	2.14
W (nm)	144.87	148.07	148.46

Even though the improved photovoltaic performance of the PSCs with doped P3HT is displayed, it shows instability over time, which implies that the Li+*t*-BP has deleterious effects on the reliability to an extent. To verify this, we measured the surface contact angle of the films to check their vulnerability to water (Figure S6). The surface contact angle of the water droplet on the perovskite layer increases after deposition of the HTL from 77° to 96° for undoped-P3HT, and 93° for doped-P3HT, indicating both the undoped and doped P3HT layers can protect the perovskite layer against moisture. Besides, we noted that the P3HT doped with Li+*t*-BP is less hydrophobic than pristine P3HT. Further, the partial evaporation of 4-tert-butylpyridine (*t*-BP) and aggregation of Li-TFSI leading to the appearance of holes in the polymer layer which in turn can facilitate the penetration of oxygen and moisture into the perovskite layer, causing the device degradation [65,66].

Conclusion

In summary, we investigated the influence of hole selective layers on the device kinetics of triple-cation-based perovskite solar cells by using doped and undoped P3HT. The hole selective layer-free PSCs demonstrated a PCE of 6.37% with apparent hysteresis whereas a higher PCE of 15.19% and 16.23% with negligible hysteresis was measured for the PSCs with undoped and doped P3HT. Impedance spectroscopy studies revealed the appearance of the negative capacitance at low frequencies, which is abundantly pronounced in the hole selective layer-free devices. We ascribed this to the interfacial interactions of migrating ions with back (Au metal) metallic contact that leads to a decrease in the recombination resistance which in turn dominates the low-frequency PSCs response and yielding a negative capacitance. Further, by performing Mott-Schottky measurements, the depletion width and the built-in potential were evaluated.

Author Contributions

H.D and N.H.H. fabricated the devices, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and prepared the initial draft, W.A provided assistance to H.D, A.B, and S.K. conceived the idea and performed the analysis of the data, S.A. supervised and directed the research. All authors contributed to the draft and prepared the final version.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or the author.

Reference

- [1] A. Kojima, K. Teshima, Y. Shirai, T. Miyasaka, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, 131, 6050.
- [2] H. S. Kim, C. R. Lee, J. H. Im, K. B. Lee, T. Moehl, A. Marchioro, S. J. Moon, R. Humphry-Baker, J. H. Yum, J. E. Moser, M. Grätzel, N. G. Park, *Sci. Rep.* **2012**, 2, 1.
- [3] P. Meredith, A. Armin, *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, 9, 1.
- [4] NREL. Best Research-Cell Efficiency Chart; **2020**; <https://www.nrel.gov/pv/cell-efficiency.html>.
- [5] M. Saliba, T. Matsui, J. Y. Seo, K. Domanski, J. P. Correa-Baena, M. K. Nazeeruddin, Shaik M. Zakeeruddin, W. Tress, A. Abate, M. Grätzel, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2016**, 9, 1989.
- [6] G. E. Eperon, S. D. Stranks, C. Menelaou, M. B. Johnston, L. M. Herz, H. J. Snaith, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2014**, 7, 982.

- [7] G. Xing, N. Mathews, S. Sun, S. S. Lim, Y. M. Lam, M. Grätzel, S. Mhaisalkar, T. C. Sum, *Science* **2013**, 342, 344.
- [8] S. I. Seok, M. Grätzel, N. G. Park, *Small* **2018**, 14, 1704177.
- [9] L. Salamandra, N. Y. Nia, M. Di Natali, C. Fazolo, S. Maiello, L. La Notte, G. Susanna, A. Pizzoleo, F. Matteocci, L. Cinà, L. Mattiello, F. Brunetti, A. Di Carlob, A. Reale, *Org. Electron.* **2019**, 69, 220.
- [10] K. Miyano, M. Yanagida, N. Tripathi, Y. Shirai, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2016**, 7, 2240.
- [11] G. Garcia-Belmonte, J. Bisquert, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2016**, 1, 683.
- [12] A. Solanki, P. Yadav, S. H. Turren-Cruz, S. S. Lim, M. Saliba, T. C. Sum, *Nano Energy* **2019**, 58, 604
- [13] B. Chen, M. Yang, S. Priya, K. Zhu, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2016**, 7, 905.
- [14] P. Calado, A. M. Telford, D. Bryant, X. Li, J. Nelson, B. C. O'Regan, P. R. Barnes, *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, 7, 1.
- [15] I. Levine, P. K. Nayak, J. T. W. Wang, N. Sakai, S. Van Reenen, T. M. Brenner, S. Mukhopadhyay, H. J. Snaith, G. Hodes, D. Cahen, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, 120, 16399.
- [16] D. A. Jacobs, Y. Wu, H. Shen, C. Barugkin, F. J. Beck, T. P. White, K. Weber, K. R. Catchpole, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, 19, 3094.
- [17] M. Pegu, S. Kazim, T. Buffeteau, D. M. Bassani, S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 4, 3130.
- [18] Q. Shen, A. Ng, Z. Ren, H. C. Gokkaya, A. B. Djurisic, J. A. Zapien, C. Surya, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, 10, 371.

- [19] A. Pockett, G. E. Eperon, T. Peltola, H. J. Snaith, A. Walker, L. M. Peter, P. J. Cameron, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2015**, 119, 3456.
- [20] Q. Dong, Y. Fang, Y. Shao, P. Mulligan, J. Qiu, L. Cao, J. Huang, *Science* **2015**, 347, 967.
- [21] P. Lopez-Varo, J. A. Jiménez-Tejada, M. García-Rosell, S. Ravishankar, G. Garcia-Belmonte, J. Bisquert, O. Almora, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, 8, 1702772.
- [22] Y. Feng, J. Bian, M. Wang, S. Wang, C. Zhang, Q. Dong, B. Zhang, Y. Shi, *Mater. Res. Bull.* **2018**, 107, 74.
- [23] D. Klotz, *Electrochem. Commun.* **2019**, 98, 58.
- [24] M. T. Khan, P. Huang, A. Almohammed, S. Kazim, S. Ahmad, *IScience* **2020**, 102024.
- [25] F. Fabregat-Santiago, M. Kulbak, A. Zohar, M. Vallés-Pelarda, G. Hodes, D. Cahen, I. Mora-Seró, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2017**, 2, 2007.
- [26] A. Guerrero, G. Garcia-Belmonte, I. Mora-Sero, J. Bisquert, Y. S. Kang, T. J. Jacobsson, J. P. Correa-Baena, A. Hagfeldt, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, 120, 8023.
- [27] E. Ghahremanirad, A. Bou, S. Olyae, J. Bisquert, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2017**, 8, 1402.
- [28] D. Moia, I. Gelmetti, P. Calado, W. Fisher, M. Stringer, O. Game, Y. Hu, P. Docampo, D. Lidzey, E. Palomares, J. Nelson, P. R. Barnes, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2019**, 12, 1296.
- [29] A. Solanki, A. Guerrero, Q. Zhang, J. Bisquert, T. C. Sum, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2019**, 11, 463.
- [30] D. A. Jacobs, H. Shen, F. Pfeffer, J. Peng, T. P. White, F. J. Beck, K. R. Catchpole, *J. Appl. Phys.* **2018**, 124, 225702.

- [31] F. Ebadi, N. Taghavinia, R. Mohammadpour, A. Hagfeldt, W. Tress, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 1.
- [32] P. Zhou, T. Bu, S. Shi, L. Li, Y. Zhang, Z. Ku, Y. Peng, J. Zhong, Y. B. Cheng, F. Huang, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2018**, *6*, 5733.
- [33] T. Gatti, F. Lamberti, P. Topolovsek, M. Abdu-Aguye, R. Sorrentino, L. Perino, M. Salerno, L. Girardi, C. Marega, G. A. Rizzi, M. A. Loi, A. Petrozza, E. Menna, *Sol. RRL* **2018**, *2*, 1800013.
- [34] S. Ahmad, R. Berger, H. U. Khan, H.-J. Butt, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2010**, *20*, 5325.
- [35] Y. Miyazawa, M. Ikegami, H. W. Chen, T. Ohshima, M. Imaizumi, K. Hirose, T. Miyasaka, *IScience* **2018**, *2*, 148.
- [36] Q. Hu, E. Rezaee, M. Li, Q. Chen, C. Li, S. Cai, H. Shan, Z. X. Xu, *Sol. RRL* **2020**, *4*, 1900340.
- [37] B. Xue, B. Vaughan, C. H. Poh, K. B. Burke, L. Thomsen, A. Stapleton, X. Zhou, G. W. Bryant, W. Belcher, P. C. Dastoor, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2010**, *114*, 15797.
- [38] T. S. Ripolles, A. Guerrero, G. Garcia-Belmonte, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2013**, *103*, 236.
- [39] P. Huang, A. Hernández, S. Kazim, J. Ortiz, Á. Sastre-Santos S. Ahmad, *Sustainable Energy Fuels* **2020**, *4*, 6188.
- [40] Y. Yang, N. D. Pham, D. Yao, L. Fan, M. T. Hoang, V. T. Tiong, Z. Wang, H. Zhu, H. Wang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 28431.
- [41] N. Alias, A. Ali Umar, N. A. A. Malek, K. Liu, X. Li, N. A. Abdullah, M. M. Rosli, M. Y. Abd Rahman, Z. Shi, X. Zhang, H. Zhang, F. Liu, J. Wang, Y. Zhan, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, *13*, 3051.

- [42] D. Pitarch-Tena, T. T. Ngo, M. Vallés-Pelarda, T. Pauporté, I. Mora-Seró, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, *3*, 1044.
- [43] T. Zhu, D. Zheng, J. Liu, L. Coolen, T. Pauporté, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12*, 37197.
- [44] J. Hang, E. J. Juárez-Pérez, I. Mora-Seró, B. Viana, T. Pauporté, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2015**, *3*, 4909.
- [45] H. Zhang, X. Qiao, Y. Shen, T. Moehl, S. M. Zakeeruddin, M. Grätzel, M. Wang, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2015**, *3*, 11762.
- [46] P. Wang, M. Ulfa, T. Pauporté, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2018**, *122*, 1973.
- [47] H. S. Kim, I. Mora-Sero, V. Gonzalez-Pedro, F. Fabregat-Santiago, E. J. Juarez-Perez, N. G. Park, J. Bisquert, *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 1.
- [48] P. Wang, Z. Shao, M. Ulfa, T. Pauporté, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2017**, *121*, 9131.
- [49] D. Zheng, T. Zhu, T. Pauporté, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 10349.
- [50] B. Tan, S. R. Raga, K. J. Rietwyk, J. Lu, S. O. Furer, J. C. Griffith, Y. B. Cheng, U. Bach, *Nano Energy* **2020**, *82*, 105658.
- [51] D. Yao, X. Mao, X. Wang, Y. Yang, N. D. Pham, A. Du, H. Wang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12*, 6651.
- [52] A. Dualé, T. Moehl, N. Tétreault, J. Teuscher, P. Gao, M. K. Nazeeruddin, M. Grätzel, *ACS nano* **2014**, *8*, 362.
- [53] R. A. Kerner, B. P. Rand, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2017**, *8*, 2298.

- [54] A. Guerrero, G. Garcia-Belmonte, I. Mora-Sero, J. Bisquert, Y. S. Kang, T. J. Jacobsson, J. P. Correa-Baena, A. Hagfeldt, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, 120, 8023.
- [55] A. Kumar, A. Rana, N. Vashistha, K. K. Garg, R. K. Singh, *Sol. Energy* **2020**, 211, 345.
- [56] H. Yang, S. Kannappan, A. S. Pandian, J. H. Jang, Y. S. Lee, W. Lu, *Nanotechnology* **2017**, 28, 445401.
- [57] W. Tress, N. Marinova, T. Moehl, S. M. Zakeeruddin, M. K. Nazeeruddin, M. Grätzel, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2015**, 8, 995.
- [58] W. Tress, M. Yavari, K. Domanski, P. Yadav, B. Niesen, J. P. C. Baena, A. Hagfeldt, M. Graetzel, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2018**, 11, 151.
- [59] M. Taukeer Khan, A. Almohammed, S. Kazim, A. Ahmad, *Chem. Rec.* **2020**, 20, 452.
- [60] J. Lee, J. D. Cohen, W. N. Shafarman, *Thin Solid Films* **2005**, 480, 336.
- [61] H. S. Duan, H. Zhou, Q. Chen, P. Sun, S. Luo, T. B. Song, B. Bob, Y. Yang, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2015**, 17, 112.
- [62] K. Gelderman, L. Lee, S. W. Donne, *J. Chem. Educ.* **2007**, 84, 685.
- [63] Q. Chen, L. Chen, F. Ye, T. Zhao, F. Tang, A. Rajagopal, Z. Jiang, S. Jiang, A. K. Y. Jen, Y. Xie, J. Cia, L. Chen, *Nano Lett.* **2017**, 17, 3231.
- [64] X. Liu, Z. Liu, H. Ye, Y. Tu, B. Sun, X. Tan, T. Shi, Z. Tang, G. Liao, *Electrochim. Acta* **2018**, 288, 115.
- [65] N. D. Pham, J. Shang, Y. Yang, M. T. Hoang, V. T. Tiong, X. Wang, L. Fan, P. Chen, L. Kou, L. Wang, H. Wang, H. *Nano Energy* **2020**, 69, 104412.

[66] S. Wang, M. Sina, P. Parikh, T. Uekert, B. Shahbazian, A. Devaraj, Y. S. Meng, *Nano Lett.* **2016**, *16*, 5594.